

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Human papillomavirus type 49, a novel papillomavirus type.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Papillomavirus types 3, 10, 38, and 49 cause flat warts: infection of the skin with a low-risk papillomavirus resulting in small, flat-topped skin growths. We compared the transcriptional properties of alpha genus HPV type 16 and beta genus HPV type 49 E6/E7 to understand novel functions of HPV49. HPV49 and HPV16 E6/E7 differed in control of keratins (e.g., KRT6C, KRT1 and KRT81) and intermediate filaments including */NA*. Type 49 and Type 16 E6/E7 were different in control of enzymes of the extracellular matrix encoded by the MMP family. Of interest, while HPV49 E6/E7 silenced PPARG, HPV16 E6/E7 activated the nuclear factor. A major molecular difference in E6/E7 functions between type 16 and type 49 HPV was control of the interferon system including the interferon system ISGs Ifi6, Ifit1 and Ifitm1.

GSE100681